

High Resolution EC Earth Porting and Benchmarking on Curie

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Abstract

The high resolution version of EC-EARTH is ported on Curie. The scalability of the code is tested up to 3500 CPU cores. An example EC-EARTH run is profiled using the TAU tool.

1. Introduction

The EC-EARTH is an earth system modeling application. The three main components of EC-EARTH are IFS (for atmosphere), NEMO (for ocean) and OASIS (for coupling). We have benchmarked a high resolution version of EC-EARTH configuration for scaling. The ocean component used for this configuration is ORCA025 which is a 1/4° global configuration. The atmosphere component uses T799 resolution. The source code of NEMO is v-3.2, IFS is Cycle 36r1 and the coupler is OASIS3. For our benchmarking and porting exercises the source code of EC-EARTH with necessary modifications, input files and run scripts were obtained from SMHI. A more recent version of EC-EARTH is also available now and will be tried subsequently. The system used for our scaling studies is Curie which is a petaflop machine in Europe.

The performance of any MPI program may depend on various components, *e.g.*, compilers, MPI libraries, network, file-system, processor technologies etc. As EC-EARTH is a large and complex program, its porting on this new machine is a considerable challenge. After porting the performance and scaling needs to be tested. The goal is to figure out the bottlenecks and to look at suitable strategies to improve the scaling.

The work is part of PRACE WP 7.2 project on petascaling of EC-EARTH. The current report contains the part that we are engaged in from WP 7.5. A more elaborate report combining documents from other contributors will be published from WP 7.2 [1].

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2. Test system

The Curie system is a Linux – infinband cluster. Each node has 4 CPU / Socket. Each socket has 8 processing cores. In this whitepaper when we use term number of MPI processes (nprocs) we mean number of processing cores as we always run 1 MPI process / core. The more details of hardware and the software of the Curie system are given in Table 1.

Table 1. Curie system hardware and software

System	Curie
Processor	Intel(R) Xeon(R) CPU X7560 @ 2.27GHz
Interconnect	InfiniBand QDR Full Fat Tree network
Node	4 CPU or Socket, 32 cores
global file-system	Lustre
Compiler	Intel compiler
MPI library	Bullxmpi

3. Compiling EC-EARTH on Curie

The compilation procedure of the EC-EARTH code is described in detail in [2]. The important thing is to set up an appropriate xml file with a description of system specific settings for package paths, compilers, flags, libraries *etc.* Some template xml files are provided in the build-config/ folder under the EC-EARTH root folder. The settings used in this work are contained in curie.xml which is given in Appendix 1. As the individual packages used in EC-EARTH have quite different build environments we use the semi-automatic utility eexcon found under the utility/ folder in the EC-EARTH root folder. This utility reads the specific xml file under the build-config folder and sets up appropriate Makefiles and other settings for each component package. We have set up a script called build.sh for compilation. The script is placed under the EC-EARTH root folder. The script build.sh is given in Appendix 2.

4. Running high resolution EC-EARTH

Compiling EC-EARTH produces multiple binaries, one each for NEMO, OASIS and IFS. The bullxmpi that is available on Curie is capable of launching MPMD runs. However, careful mapping of binaries to physical cores is important for better performance.

An EC-EARTH run requires a large number of input files. These are either namelist or data files. The namelist type files contain different parameter values which control the flow of run. The data files generally contain initial / boundary / restart values obtained from some previous runs or from some other experiments. The data files are stored in a common place and accessed from there.

The EC-EARTH run is started by a run script. The run script does three things – 1) copies/symlinks relevant data files in the run directory, 2) creates namelist files based on parameters provided in the run script and 3) launches the MPI job. A typical run script is given in Appendix 3. The run script is given to the job scheduler which starts the job script when the requested resources are allocated for the run. As EC-EARTH is a multi-binary run, an exact specification of the binary – rank – node mapping is important for performance. For best performance each component runs on a specific group of nodes. Also, due to the specific requirement of EC-EARTH, OASIS should get the $0 - (oas_numproc - 1)$ ranks, where *oas_numproc* is the number of OASIS MPI processes. For the bullx MPI implementation this is achieved by creating an appfile and then giving the appfile to mpirun, e.g.,

```
mpirun -f appfile.
```

A typical appfile looks like:

```
-hostfile oas_nodes -np 10 -x LD_LIBRARY_PATH -x OASIS3 -x OASIS3DEBUGLEVEL -x  
LOCAL_DEFINITION_TEMPLATES oasis3.MPI1.x  
-hostfile ifs_nodes -np 512 -x LD_LIBRARY_PATH -x DR_HOOK_IGNORE_SIGNALS -x OASIS3 -x  
OASIS3DEBUGLEVEL -x LOCAL_DEFINITION_TEMPLATES ifsmaster-eexcon -v ecmwf -e HRES  
-hostfile nem_nodes -np 320 -x LD_LIBRARY_PATH -x opa-eexcon
```

In the above appfile example OASIS runs on 10 CPU cores, IFS runs on 512 CPU cores and NEMO runs on 320 CPU cores. The OASIS, IFS and NEMO binaries execute on the nodes specified in files *oas_nodes*, *ifs_nodes* and *nem_nodes* respectively. The appfile and the nodelist files (*oas_nodes*, *ifs_nodes* and *nem_nodes*) are generated dynamically for every run based on the parameters specified in step 1 above.

5. Scaling of High resolution EC-EARTH on Curie

The scaling of an EC-EARTH run depends on the choice of input parameters, especially the coupling frequency, i/o frequency *etc.* We have chosen the following parameters for our runs:

```
cpl freq = 3 hrs  
run length = 48 hrs  
ifs time step = 720 s  
Frequency of history write ups = 30 IFS time steps  
Frequency of spectral diagnostics = 5 time steps  
  
NEMO time step=1200 s  
LIM time step=3600 s  
NEMO frequency of write in the output file = 72 NEMO time steps
```

In a 48 hour run we have all the significant steps repeated a number of times. So although the total run-time is small, it is indicative of scaling behavior. The results of our runs are shown in Table 2 and Figures 1 and 2. In EC-EARTH time steps there are distinct computational steps and i/o steps respectively called comp and i/o in Table 2. During comp steps there is no disk writing or inter binary communication between IFS – NEMO – OASIS. During this steps IFS and NEMO run independently while OASIS waits. During i/o steps there is disk writing and communication between IFS – NEMO – OASIS. Normally there are few comp steps followed by a i/o step. The version of EC-EARTH that we use in that each NEMO rank and each IFS rank writes data files.

Table 2. EC-EARTH run times

# MPI processes				# step	average time/step (s)		
Total	NEMO	IFS	OASIS		only comp steps	i/o steps	All steps
394	256	128	10	240	6.61	15.21	8.30
650	256	384	10	240	2.55	5.92	3.20
778	256	512	10	240	2.03	4.76	2.55
906	256	640	10	240	1.72	4.05	2.15
1034	256	768	10	240	1.53	3.54	1.90
1162	256	896	10	240	1.40	3.24	1.74
1290	256	1024	10	240	1.28	2.95	1.59
1418	256	1152	10	240	1.17	2.68	1.44
1546	256	1280	10	240	1.09	2.53	1.35
1610	320	1280	10	240	1.11	2.62	1.38
1866	320	1536	10	240	1.02	2.62	1.31
2634	320	2304	10	240	0.83	2.86	1.20
3402	320	3072	10	240	0.81	2.87	1.21
3482	400	3072	10	240	0.81	2.66	1.17

Fig. 1. EC-EARTH scaling graph

Fig. 2. EC-EARTH scaling efficiency w.r.t. 1034 core run.

6. Profiling with TAU

TAU is an open-source profiling and tracing toolkit for performance analysis of parallel programs. The TAU tool was installed on Curie. EC-EARTH was compiled with TAU. The TAU compiler puts instrumentation calls in the source code and then compiles with the configured compiler (the Intel compiler in our case). When this instrumented code is run it produces function profile data. This data can be visualized using the ParaProf toolkit. We ran EC-EARTH with TAU on 394 CPU cores, with OASIS on ranks 0 – 9, IFS on ranks 10 – 137 and NEMO on ranks 138 – 393. Figure 3 shows the visualization of the profiled runs. The colored legends refer to different functions and their total execution time. In actual GUI these legends are click-able and can give more detailed information. In figures 3 – 6 few processes from each binary are shown more clearly.

Fig. 3. EC-EARTH run with TAU profiler

The light blue coloured legend in the figure 3 represent the MPI_Recv time. In Figure 4 more details of MPI_Recv time for different ranks are shown. Figures 3 and 4 both show that the OASIS and NEMO processes are waiting in MPI_Recv whereas IFS spends little time in MPI_Recv. This clearly indicates a load imbalance for the three binaries. In the coupled EC-EARTH runs, IFS and NEMO exchange data via the OASIS coupler every few

time steps. In this run both OASIS and NEMO are waiting for IFS. The next most time consuming MPI routine for this run is MPI_Wait which is shown by the red bars in Figure 3. MPI_Wait is most important for IFS runs followed by OASIS. NEMO spends very little time in MPI_Wait as can be seen in Figure 5. IFS interacts with OASIS through the prism_put_proto and prism_get_proto routines. These routines do not use MPI_Wait. Hence the time spent by IFS in MPI_Wait is due to IFS's internal communications. Another MPI routine that takes substantial time in this run is the MPI_Alltoallv which is shown by the green bars in Figure 3. MPI_Alltoallv is called only in IFS as is shown in Figure 6. The other routines which take substantial time according to the profile are different computational routines. The TAU profiler can show many details about the time spent in different loops, actual FLOPS of subroutines and loops *etc.* A more detailed information giving timeline of function calls can be done in TAU by tracing the runs. However for tracing a 394 MPI process run the amount of data generated is so huge that we could analyse it further. This is generally the problem of tracing with other tools also. As TAU is an open source tool we are trying to implement external trigger mechanism for tracing on/off.

Fig. 4. MPI_Recv time for different ranks

Fig. 5. MPI_Wait time for different ranks.

Fig. 6. Time spent in MPI_Alltoallv by different ranks.

7. Discussion

We have run high resolution EC-EARTH simulations on up to 3500 MPI processes. As EC-EARTH is a multi binary run its scaling is dependent on scaling of individual components as well as the coupling overhead. If one component is slower than the other one then the faster binary has to wait for the slower binary to reach the synchronization stage. Thus it is important to suitably distribute the available processors amongst the three binaries of EC-EARTH. The load balancing between three binaries of OASIS, NEMO and IFS is obtained by trial and error method. The main simulation is carried out by NEMO and IFS while OASIS is active only at coupling stage. The OASIS runtime is small and there is not much impact on scaling of OASIS number of processors. Hence we keep OASIS number of processors fixed at 10. We vary NEMO and IFS processor numbers. We start with NEMO and IFS number of processors as 256 and 128 respectively. Then we increase IFS processor numbers. This improves the step times as can be seen in Table 2. However there is no accurate method to decide the optimal ratio of NEMO and IFS processor numbers. We do this by trial and error method over repeated runs. The efficiency of parallel run is defined as $e = t_n / (t_N * p)$, where n and N are the processor numbers for two runs with $n < N$ and $p = N/n$. If $n = 1$ then efficiency is measured w.r.t serial run. If serial run is not possible due to memory or some other resource constraints then n is chosen at some minimum possible value. In case of EC-EARTH choosing the reference n value is difficult. If we choose $n = 394$ as the reference run then the subsequent wider runs show $e > 1$. This however may not be due to some super linear scaling. In our opinion for $n = 394$ run the processor ratio between the three binaries as shown in Table 2 were not optimal. There was huge load imbalance. So we do not take $n = 394$ as our reference run. We choose our reference run as the run which is most efficient according to Table 2. The most efficient run is obtained at around 1034 MPI processes. We take $n = 1034$ as our reference run. We show the efficiency graph in Figure 2. At $N = 3500$ the efficiency is near 0.5. The drop in efficiency may be due to lack of scaling of individual components or load imbalance. When EC-EARTH is run with less than 1034 MPI processes, e.g., $N = 394$ the $e < 1$. We guess this is because for our choice of processor ratios between NEMO and IFS as shown in Table 2 NEMO finish earlier and wait for the IFS processes.

Some time steps have only computation. A few steps additionally have i/o. These steps are significantly slower. We have shown in Table 2 the average time of computation-only steps, i/o steps, and combined i/o and computation steps. This gives a hint about which steps are bottleneck in the overall scaling. The i/o steps are 2 – 3 times more time consuming than the computational steps. However, in our experiment every 30th time step (every 6th hour) is an i/o step. The actual impact of the i/o steps will depend on the i/o frequency for a particular experiment. Another aspect related to i/o is the variability in time from one i/o step to the next – some are much slower than others. This is because of the load on the file-system from other programs. However, on Curie the scaling of the i/o steps is consistent with that of the computational steps. This is because of the fast global lustre filesystem.

We have analyzed the file-access pattern of IFS. We found that a few small files are repeatedly opened and read. These files contain only a few kilobytes and could easily be read just once and kept in some variable for future access. This could improve the file i/o considerably.

Acknowledgments

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References

1. Performance Analysis of EC-EARTH 3.1, http://prace-ri.eu/IMG/pdf/Performance_Analysis_of_EC-EARTH_3-1.pdf
2. Guide for EC-EARTH Compiling and running. Available with EC-EARTH source code. The file `compiling-and-running-short-guide.pdf` is present in the `doc/` folder under the EC-EARTH root folder.

Appendix 1

#file : ~/config/scripts/ecearth_hres/curie.xml

```
<experiment>

  <!-- FILESET "default" <<< -->
  <fileset longname="Default fileset" name="default">

    <translation longname="Nemo makefile configuration" name="nemo_makefile_config">
      <template filename="../nemo3-orca025/util/Makefile.d/Makefile.config.eexcon.tpl"/>
      <target filename="../nemo3-orca025/util/Makefile.d/Makefile.config.eexcon"/>
    </translation>

    <translation longname="Nemo global definition file" name="nemo_aa_make_gdef">
      <template filename="../nemo3-orca025/util/AA_make.gdef.tpl"/>
      <target filename="../nemo3-orca025/util/AA_make.gdef"/>
    </translation>

    <translation longname="Nemo ... file" name="nemo_par_oce">
      <template filename="../nemo3-orca025/modeles/NEMO/OPA_SRC/par_oce.F90.tpl"/>
      <target filename="../nemo3-orca025/modeles/NEMO/OPA_SRC/par_oce.F90"/>
    </translation>

    <translation longname="IFS/36 makefile configuration" name="ifs36_makefile_config">
      <template filename="../ifs-36r1/Makefile.d/Makefile.config.eexcon.tpl"/>
      <target filename="../ifs-36r1/Makefile.d/Makefile.config.eexcon"/>
    </translation>

    <translation longname="OASIS makefile configuration" name="oasis_makefile_config">
      <template filename="../oasis3/util/make_dir/Makefile.d/Makefile.config.eexcon.tpl"/>
      <target filename="../oasis3/util/make_dir/Makefile.d/Makefile.config.eexcon"/>
    </translation>

  </fileset>
  <!-- END of FILESET "default" >>> -->

  <!-- PLATFORM "curie-intel-bullmpi" <<< -->
  <!--
  HOST:          curie.ccc.cea.fr
  ARCH:          linux_x86_64
  CPU MODEL:     Quad-Core AMD Opteron Processor 2374 HE ## check
  USER:         ufla
  COMPILER:     Intel compiler (icc+ifort)
  MPI:          Bull MPI
  BLAS/LAPACK:  Intel MKL
  -->
  <platform name="curie-intel-bullmpi">

    <param name="ECEARTH_BASE_DIR"
          longname="EC-Earth base directory"
          type="PATH">
      /ccc/work/cont005/pawp72/basuc/ecearth3-r263/ecearth_hres
    </param>

    <!-- MPI -->
    <param name="MPI_BASE_DIR"
          longname="MPI base directory"
          type="PATH">
    </param>

    <param name="MPI_INC_SUBDIR"
```

```

        longname="MPI include directory relative to base dir"
        type="PATH">
</param>

<param name="MPI_LIB_SUBDIR"
        longname="MPI lib directory relative to base dir"
        type="PATH">
</param>

<param name="MPI_LIBS_WITHOUT_L"
        longname="MPI libraries (without -l prefix)"
        type="STRING">
</param>

<!-- LAPACK -->
<param name="LAPACK_BASE_DIR"
        longname="LAPACK base directory"
        type="PATH">
    /usr/local/Intel_compilers/c/composerxe-2011.3.174/mkl
</param>

<param name="LAPACK_LIB_SUBDIR"
        longname="LAPACK lib directory relative to base dir"
        type="PATH">
    lib/intel64
</param>

<param name="LAPACK_LIBS_WITHOUT_L"
        longname="LAPACK libraries (without -l prefix)"
        type="STRING">
    mkl_lapack95_lp64 mkl_intel_lp64 mkl_sequential mkl_core pthread
</param>

<!-- NetCDF -->
<param name="NETCDF_BASE_DIR"
        longname="NetCDF base directory"
        type="PATH">
    /usr/local/netcdf-4.1.1
</param>

<param name="NETCDF_INC_SUBDIR"
        longname="NetCDF include directory relative to base dir"
        type="PATH">
    include
</param>

<param name="NETCDF_LIB_SUBDIR"
        longname="NetCDF lib directory relative to base dir"
        type="PATH">
    lib
</param>

<param name="NETCDF_LIBS_WITHOUT_L"
        longname="NetCDF libraries (without -l prefix)"
        type="STRING">
    netcdff netcdf
</param>

<!-- MAKE -->
<param name="MAKE"
        longname="Make command (GNU make >3.81 needed!)"
        type="STRING">
    make
</param>

```

```

<!-- F90 Compiler -->
<param name="F90"
      longname="F90 Compiler"
      type="STRING">
      mpif90
</param>

<param name="F90FLAGS"
      longname="General F90 flags for compiling"
      type="STRING">
      -O2 -g -traceback -vec-report0 -r8
</param>

<!-- C Compiler -->
<param name="CC"
      longname="C Compiler"
      type="STRING">
      mpicc
</param>

<param name="CFLAGS"
      longname="General C flags for compiling"
      type="STRING">
      -O2 -g -traceback
</param>

<!-- Linker -->
<param name="LD"
      longname="Linker"
      type="STRING">
      mpif90
</param>

<param name="LDFLAGS"
      longname="General flags for linking"
      type="STRING">
      -O2 -g -traceback
</param>

<!-- Library builder -->
<param name="AR"
      longname="Command for building libraries from object files (usually ar)"
      type="STRING">
      ar
</param>

<param name="ARFLAGS"
      longname="Flags for library building command (When using ar: include u)"
      type="STRING">
      curv
</param>

<!-- C Preprocessor -->
<param name="CPP"
      longname="C preprocessor command"
      type="STRING">
      mpicc
</param>

<param name="CPPFLAGS"
      longname="C preprocessor flags"
      type="STRING">
      -P -C
</param>

```

```

<!-- OASIS specific stuff -->
<param name="OASIS_ADD_F90FLAGS"
      longname="More F90 flags for Oasis"
      type="STRING">
  -mcmmodel=medium -l32 -check pointers -check uninit
</param>

<param name="OASIS_ADD_CPPDEFS"
      longname="More CPP/FPP macros for Oasis"
      type="STRING">
  use_oasis_para
</param>

<param name="OASIS_ADD_LDFLAGS"
      longname="More LD flags for Oasis"
      type="STRING">
  -mcmmodel=medium
</param>

<!-- NEMO specific stuff -->
<param name="NEMO_ADD_F90FLAGS"
      longname="More F90 flags for Nemo"
      type="STRING">
  -module $(MODDIR) -mcmmodel=medium -check pointers -check uninit
</param>

<param name="NEMO_ADD_LDFLAGS"
      longname="More LD flags for Nemo"
      type="STRING">
  -shared-intel -mcmmodel=medium
</param>

<!-- IFS specific stuff -->
<param name="IFS_FPPDEFS"
      longname="Preprocessor defs for IFS sources"
      type="STRING">
  linux LINUX LITTLE LITTLE_ENDIAN POINTER_64 BLAS
</param>

<param name="IFS_AUX_ADD_F90FLAGS"
      longname="More F90 flags for ifs/ifsaux"
      type="STRING">
</param>

<!-- EMOS specific stuff -->
<param name="EMOS_ADD_FFLAGS"
      longname="Additional Fortran compiler flags for EMOSLIB"
      type="STRING">
  -i4
</param>

<param name="EMOS_FPPDEFS"
      longname="Fortran preprocessor defs for EMOSLIB"
      type="STRING">
  linux LITTLE_ENDIAN POINTER_64 INTEGER_IS_INT REAL_8 REAL_BIGGER_THAN_INTEGER
</param>

<param name="EMOS_CPPDEFS"
      longname="C preprocessor defs for EMOSLIB"
      type="STRING">
  $(EMOS_FPPDEFS) FOPEN64
</param>

<!-- F90 Dependency generator -->
<param name="MAKEDEPF90"

```

```

        longname="F90 dependency generator"
        type="STRING">
    $(ECEARTH_BASE_DIR)/util/makedepf90/bin/makedepf90
</param>

</platform>
<!-- END of PLATFORM "curie-intel-bullmpi" >>> -->

<!-- MODEL "nemo" <<< -->
<model longname="Nemo ocean model" name="nemo">

    <param name="numproc_i" longname="Number of procs along i direction" type="INTEGER">
        20
    </param>

    <param name="numproc_j" longname="Number of procs along j direction" type="INTEGER">
        20
    </param>

</model>
<!-- END of MODEL "nemo" >>> -->

</experiment>

```

Appendix 2

#file: ~/config/scripts/ecearth_hres/build.sh

```
pwd=`pwd`
cd ifs-36r1

../util/eexcon/eexcon -p curie-intel-bullmpi -f default ../build-config/curie.xml
if [ "$?" = "1" ]; then
    echo "exit 1"
    exit
fi

cd $pwd/oasis3/util/make_dir

make BUILD_ARCH=eexcon -f TopMakefileOasis3 realclean
make -f TopMakefileOasis3 BUILD_ARCH=eexcon

    cd $pwd/nemo3-orca025/modeles/UTIL/
    ./fait_config ORCA025_LIM2
    cd ../../util/
    ./ins_make -t ecearth3 -m MPI1
    cd ../config/ORCA025_LIM2/

make BUILD_ARCH=eexcon clean
make BUILD_ARCH=eexcon

cd $pwd/ifs-36r1
make BUILD_ARCH=eexcon realclean
make -j 8 BUILD_ARCH=eexcon lib
make BUILD_ARCH=eexcon master
```

Appendix 3

```
## Typical run script
#!/bin/sh
#SBATCH -t 60
#SBATCH -N 13 -n 416
####SBATCH -o out/out_10_256_128
#SBATCH -o dump

IFS_V=8
IFS_W=16
NEM_I=16
NEM_J=16
OAS_N=10
eearth_base_dir=/ccc/work/cont005/pawp72/basuc/eearth3-r263/eearth_hres
source ~/config/env.eearth_hres_tau
set -ue

here=`pwd`

# =====
# *** BEGIN Configuration
# =====

# -----
# *** General configuration
# -----

run_arch=intel-bullmpi

# Experiment name (exactly 4 letters!)
exp_name=HRES
ifs_grid=T799
nem_grid=ORCA025

# Directories
#eearth_base_dir=/ccc/work/cont005/pawp72/basuc/eearth/eearth3-r263
start_dir=${PWD}
ctrl_file_dir=${start_dir}/ctrl
run_dir=/ccc/scratch/cont005/pawp72/basuc/run/${exp_name}
ini_data_dir=/ccc/work/cont005/pawp72/basuc/data/${ifs_grid}-${nem_grid}

# ...
run_length_hrs=48
cpl_freq_hrs=3
```

```

run_length_prev_hrs=0

# ...
proc_per_node=32
build_arch=eexcon

# -----
# *** IFS configuration
# -----

ifs_numproc_v=$IFS_V
ifs_numproc_w=$IFS_W
(( ifs_numproc = $ifs_numproc_v * $ifs_numproc_w ))

ifs_exe_file=${eearth_base_dir}/ifs-36r1/bin/ifsmaster-${build_arch}

emos_gribtemplates=${eearth_base_dir}/ifs-36r1/src/emos-370/gribtemplates

ifs_lastout=true

ifs_tstep=720

(( ifs_run_length = $run_length_hrs * 3600 / $ifs_tstep ))

(( ifs_output_freq = 6 * 3600 / $ifs_tstep ))
(( ifs_di_freq = 1 * 3600 / $ifs_tstep ))

(( ifs_cpl_freq = $cpl_freq_hrs * 3600 / $ifs_tstep ))

# -----
# *** Nemo/LIM configuration
# -----

# 1 NEMO not compiled with key_iomput (classic IOIPSL outputs)
#         nem_ios=-1
# 2 NEMO compiled with key_iomput (IOM outputs without separate ioserver)
#         nem_ios=0

```

```

# 3 NEMO compiled with key_iomput (IOM outputs with separate ioserver)
#             nem_ios=1
nem_ios=-1

[ $nem_ios -gt 0 ] && useserv=.true. || useserv=.false.

nem_numproc_i=$NEM_I
nem_numproc_j=$NEM_J

nem_exe_dir=${ecearth_base_dir}/nemo3-orca025/bin
nem_exe_file=${nem_exe_dir}/opa-${build_arch}-${nem_numproc_i}x${nem_numproc_j}
[ $nem_ios -gt -1 ] && nem_exe_file=${nem_exe_file}-iomod
ios_exe_file=${nem_exe_dir}/ioserver-${build_arch}

nem_numproc=$(( nem_numproc_i * nem_numproc_j ))

nem_tstep=1200
lim_tstep=3600

(( nem_run_length = $run_length_hrs * 3600 / $nem_tstep ))

# daily output
(( nem_output_freq = 86400 / $nem_tstep ))

(( nem_bc_compute = $lim_tstep / $nem_tstep ))

# -----
# *** Oasis configuration
# -----

oas_namcut_script=${start_dir}/namsplit.pl

oas_numproc=$OAS_N

oas_exe_file=${ecearth_base_dir}/oasis3/${build_arch}/bin/oasis3.MPI1.x

# =====
# *** END of Configuration
# =====

```

```

function cleanup()
{
    set +u

    if [ -r ${tempfile} ]
    then
        rm -f ${tempfile}
    fi

    stdout_file=${start_dir}/out/job.${SP_JID}.out

    if [ -r ${stdout_file} -a -d ${run_dir} ]
    then
        cp ${stdout_file} ${run_dir}
    fi
}

trap 'cleanup' 0 1 2 15

function info()
{
    echo "*II* $@"
}

function error()
{
    echo "*EE* $@"
    exit 1
}

# -----
# *** This is where the code begins ...
# -----

export PATH=/ccc/work/cont005/pawp72/basuc/software/grib_api-1.9.9/bin/:$PATH

# Create/clean run dir

```

```

if [ ! -d ${run_dir} ]
then
    mkdir -p ${run_dir}
else
    rm -fr ${run_dir}/*
fi

# Go to run_dir. Everything is done from here
cd ${run_dir}

# Link executables
ln -s ${ifs_exe_file}
ln -s ${oas_exe_file}
ln -s ${nem_exe_file}
[ $nem_ios -gt 0 ] && ln -s ${ios_exe_file}

# Create IFS and Nemo/LIM namelists
if (( $ifs_numproc > 512 ))
then
    . ${ctrl_file_dir}/namelist.ifs36.sh > fort.4
else
    . ${ctrl_file_dir}/namelist.ifs36_test.sh > fort.4
fi
. ${ctrl_file_dir}/namelist.nemo.sh > namelist
. ${ctrl_file_dir}/namelist.lim2.sh > namelist_ice
[ $nem_ios -gt -1 ] && . ${ctrl_file_dir}/namelist.ios.sh > xmlio_server.def
. ${ctrl_file_dir}/namcouple.sh.seq > namcouple_tmp
if (( $nem_ios < 1 ))
then
    sed -e /IOS_PROCS/d -e s/'.'ionemo/"2 ifsmo oceanx"/ namcouple_tmp > namcouple
else
    sed -e s/IOS_PROCS/"1 0"/ namcouple_tmp > namcouple
fi

# Split Oasis namcouple file
${oas_namcut_script} ${oas_numproc} namcouple

# IFS data files
ln -s ${ini_data_dir}/ifs/ICMGGa071INIUA ICMGG${exp_name}INIUA

```

```

ln -s ${ini_data_dir}/ifs/ICMGa071INIT ICMGG${exp_name}INIT
ln -s ${ini_data_dir}/ifs/ICMSHa071INIT ICMSH${exp_name}INIT
ln -s ${ini_data_dir}/ifs/postins
ln -s ${ini_data_dir}/ifs/dirlist
ln -s ${ini_data_dir}/ifs/rtables/* .

mkdir -p gribtemplates
ln -s ${eearth_base_dir}/ifs-36r1/src/emos-370/gribtemplates/* gribtemplates/

# ...
tempfile=tmp.$$
grib_set -s dataDate=19951215 \
        ${ini_data_dir}/ifs/ICMCL-split_12 \
        ICMCL${exp_name}INIT
for m in 01 02 03 04 05 06 07 08 09 10 11 12
do
    grib_set -s dataDate=1996${m}15 \
            ${ini_data_dir}/ifs/ICMCL-split_${m} \
            ${tempfile}
    cat ${tempfile} >> ICMCL${exp_name}INIT
done
grib_set -s dataDate=19970115 \
        ${ini_data_dir}/ifs/ICMCL-split_01 \
        ${tempfile}
cat ${tempfile} >> ICMCL${exp_name}INIT
rm -f ${tempfile}

# Nemo data files
ln -s ${ini_data_dir}/nemo/bathy_meter.nc
ln -s ${ini_data_dir}/nemo/coordinates.nc

ln -s ${ini_data_dir}/nemo/data_1m_potential_temperature_nomask_01.nc
data_1m_potential_temperature_nomask_1.nc
ln -s ${ini_data_dir}/nemo/data_1m_potential_temperature_nomask_02.nc
data_1m_potential_temperature_nomask_2.nc
ln -s ${ini_data_dir}/nemo/data_1m_potential_temperature_nomask_03.nc
data_1m_potential_temperature_nomask_3.nc

ln -s ${ini_data_dir}/nemo/data_1m_salinity_nomask_01.nc data_1m_salinity_nomask_1.nc
ln -s ${ini_data_dir}/nemo/data_1m_salinity_nomask_02.nc data_1m_salinity_nomask_2.nc
ln -s ${ini_data_dir}/nemo/data_1m_salinity_nomask_03.nc data_1m_salinity_nomask_3.nc

```

```

ln -s ${ini_data_dir}/nemo/ahmcoef

# IOM data file
[ $nem_ios -gt -1 ] && ln -s ${ini_data_dir}/nemo/iodef.orca025.xml iodef.xml

# Oasis name_table file
ln -s ${ini_data_dir}/oasis/cf_name_table.txt

# Oasis weight dirs
ln -s ${ini_data_dir}/oasis/areas.nc
ln -s ${ini_data_dir}/oasis/grids.nc
ln -s ${ini_data_dir}/oasis/masks.nc

#note: some rmp_$n.nc files are useless
for (( n=0; n<oas_numproc; n++ ))
do
    ln -s ${ini_data_dir}/oasis/wgt/rmp_A400_to_Ot25_GAUSWGT.nc rmp_A400_to_Ot25_GAUSWGT_$n.nc
    ln -s ${ini_data_dir}/oasis/wgt/rmp_Ot25_to_A400_GAUSWGT.nc rmp_Ot25_to_A400_GAUSWGT_$n.nc
done
unset n

# Oasis restart files
cpl_fields="TAUX_OCE TAUY_OCE TAUX_ICE TAUY_ICE \
           QS___OCE QS___ICE QNS___OCE QNS___ICE DQDT_ICE \
           PRCP_LIQ PRCP_SOL EVAP_TOT EVAP_ICE RNF___OCE \
           O_SSTSST O_TepIce O_AlIce OIceFrac O_IceTck O_SnwTck"

for f in ${cpl_fields}
do
    cp ${ini_data_dir}/oasis/rst/$f .
done

export DR_HOOK_IGNORE_SIGNALS='-1'
export OASIS3=yes
export OASIS3DEBUGLEVEL=2
export LOCAL_DEFINITION_TEMPLATES=${emos_gribtemplates}

ulimit -s unlimited

```

```

str_ios=""

# Compute node distribution
set +u
VARS="-x LD_LIBRARY_PATH -x DR_HOOK_IGNORE_SIGNALS -x OASIS3 -x OASIS3DEBUGLEVEL -x
LOCAL_DEFINITION_TEMPLATES "
oas_numproc_orig=$oas_numproc
ifs_numproc_orig=$ifs_numproc
nem_numproc_orig=$nem_numproc
rm -rf oas_nodes ifs_nodes nem_nodes
touch oas_nodes ifs_nodes nem_nodes
/ccc/cont005/home/pawp72/basuc/scripts/nodes.sh

for node in `cat nodes`
do
  if (( oas_numproc > 0 ))
  then
    n=$((proc_per_node<oas_numproc?proc_per_node:oas_numproc))
    str_oas="${str_oas}${node} ${n} "
    oas_numproc=$((oas_numproc-n))
    echo "${node}" >> oas_nodes
    continue
  fi
  if (( ifs_numproc > 0 ))
  then
    n=$(( proc_per_node<ifs_numproc?proc_per_node:ifs_numproc ))
    str_ifs="${str_ifs}${node} ${n} "
    ifs_numproc=$(( ifs_numproc - n ))
    echo "${node}" >> ifs_nodes
    continue
  fi
  if (( nem_numproc > 0 ))
  then
    n=$(( proc_per_node<nem_numproc?proc_per_node:nem_numproc ))
    str_nem="${str_nem}${node} ${n} "
    nem_numproc=$(( nem_numproc - n ))
    echo "${node}" >> nem_nodes
    continue
  fi
done

```

```

echo "-hostfile oas_nodes -np $oas_numproc_orig $VARS oasis3.MPI1.x" > appfile
echo "-hostfile ifs_nodes -np $ifs_numproc_orig $VARS ifsmaster-`${build_arch}` -v ecmwf -e
`${exp_name}` " >> appfile
echo "-hostfile nem_nodes -np $nem_numproc_orig $VARS opa-`${build_arch}`-
`${nem_numproc_i}`x`${nem_numproc_j}`" >> appfile

set -u
if (( oas_numproc > 0 || ifs_numproc > 0 || nem_numproc > 0 ))
then
    info "Oasis (missing ${oas_numproc} procs): `${str_oas}`"
    info "IFS (missing ${ifs_numproc} procs): `${str_ifs}`"
    info "Nemo (missing ${nem_numproc} procs): `${str_nem}`"
    error "Not enough nodes available!"
else
    info "======"
    info "Node/proc distribution:"
    info "-----"
    info "Oasis: `${str_oas}`"
    info "IFS: `${str_ifs}`"
    info "Nemo: `${str_nem}`"
    info "======"
fi

t_start=`date +%s`
mpirun -app appfile
t_stop=`date +%s`
t_run=$((t_stop-t_start))
t_hrs=$((t_run/3600))
t_min=$((t_run-(t_hrs*3600))/60)
t_sec=$((t_run-(t_hrs*3600)-(t_min*60))

info "==> Finished run after ${t_hrs}hrs ${t_min}min ${t_sec}sec"

exit 0

```